

INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIOR OF SOCIAL SCIENCE FACULTY: A STUDY OF UNIVERSITIES OF PUNJAB, HARYANA AND CHANDIGARH

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the research was to examine the information-seeking behaviour of social science faculties of Panjab University (PU), Punjabi University (PbiU), Guru Nanak Dev University (GNDU), Maharshi Dayanand University (MDU) and Kurukshetra University (KU). A structured questionnaire was used as a data gathering tool and descriptive statistical methods along with Chi-Square tests, t-test and ANOVA tests were applied for the analysis of data. The libraries of all the sample universities were providing e-resources to the social science faculty. However, the libraries of KU, MDU and PU have better hardware infrastructure facilities, with PU and KU topping the chart with better Internet facilities. Further, these libraries maintain campus local area network and purchase required software. Due to e-literacy and easy availability, usage of electronic resources has increased. The participants prefer internet resources than online databases. UGC-Infonet e-journals and JStor online databases are preferred. Websites and e-mail were the two most preferred internet resources for remaining updated and to gather information. Journals and textbooks were the most preferred information sources, browsing in library shelves and by looking for citations in journal articles were the most frequently used tools to get access to the documents. Information scattered in too many sources was the major barrier in seeking information. Based on the research findings, the suggestions have been provided to improve the current information services of the libraries and to devise the efficient information support system according to the electronic environment to fully cater to the information needs of social science faculty members.